

Carbon dots as fluorescent sensor for detection of explosive nitrocompounds

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ABSTRACT

Highly and stable fluorescent carbon dots (CQDs), with $\lambda_{\text{ex}}/\lambda_{\text{em}} = 350/465$ nm were obtained using a strong acid oxidation of activated carbon in aqueous suspension. The nanoparticles had a mean size of 12 nm and quantum yield of 3.94%. After functionalization with amine groups by PAMAM-NH₂ dendrimer (CQDs@PAMAM-NH₂), the size of particles increased and aggregates of 65 nm were formed. Quantum yield also increased to 6.33%. CQDs were characterized by various analytical techniques including ATR-FTIR, Raman, XPS and fluorescence spectroscopies. The prepared CQDs@PAMAM-NH₂ were used as fluorescent ratiometric nanosensor of 4-chloro-2,6-dinitroaniline, which is a constituent of explosives. As a result of interactions, the fluorescence at 465 nm was quenched. Moreover, a new band at 507 nm emerged and it is linked to a charge transfer and the formation of a Meisenheimer complex. A ratio of fluorescence intensities at 465 and 507 nm (I_{465}/I_{507}) is used for a ratiometric fluorescence sensing. A linear detection ranges from 1.0×10^{-5} to 6.0×10^{-4} M with a detection limit of 2 μM and accuracy of 0.85% as standard relative deviation (RSD, $n = 10$). The detection accuracy in the presence of other nitrocompounds was 2.80% as RSD.

1. Introduction

Inorganic quantum dots (QDs) have been widely used in various fields ranging from optoelectronics to biosensors because of their unique properties including photo-stability and brightness. Even though the advantages are in the stability and chemical coupling inherent to the colloidal state of QDs [1], the drawback of their applications are in an intrinsic cytotoxicity, mainly attributed to cadmium QDs [2–9]. Therefore, metal free QDs with luminescent properties comparable to those of QDs have received much attention recently [10,11].

Carbon quantum dots (CQDs) are a new class of carbon nano-materials of 10 nm in diameter which are considered as being able to overcome the restrictions attributed to QDs. They exhibit high water solubility, bright photoluminescence in the visible spectrum, low toxicity, good biocompatibility, high stability and are easy to

functionalize [12–14]. The unique properties of CQDs lead to their promising applications in bio-sensing, cellular imaging, drug delivery and catalysis [14]. Inspired by the variety of their usage, there is a growing interest in the synthesis of new carbon dots [15–18]. The photoluminescence of CQDs may be tunable by changing their size, depending on the synthesis method, and by introducing various functional groups at the graphitic sheet edges [19]. So far their photoluminescence mechanism has been explained based on the edge structure, surface defects, doping, and triple ground state of carbene like free zig-zag sites [20], quantum size, and electron-hole recombination [13]. Another interesting property observed in some CQDs is the multi-photon excitation or up-conversion, which is considered as an anti-Stokes transition [21,22].

Synthetic methods used to obtain CQDs are classified into two categories [23]: **i**) Top-down procedures in which graphite powder or multi-walled carbon nanotubes are exposed to harsh physical or chemical conditions such arch discharge, laser ablation, electrochemical methods [24–27] and **ii**) Bottom-up synthetic approaches, where small molecules such as carbohydrates are the

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sources of CQDs by applying external energy as, for instance, ultrasonication, microwave pyrolysis, and heating [28–32]. This leads to materials of diverse properties that make it difficult to understand the mechanism of CQDs luminescence [33].

Strategies for tuning the surface chemistry include a heteroatom doping and functionalization. In the case of the latter approach the edge groups, like carboxyl and hydroxyl groups, are used as reactive sites [34,35]. While carboxyl groups induce non-radiative recombination of electron-hole pairs, the functionalization of CQDs with amine groups decreases surface defects and consequently diminishes the non-radiative recombination process, resulting in a fluorescence enhancement and a photoluminescence blue shift [36]. Examples are passivation with polyethylenimine/poly(amino amine), 1,2-ethylenediamine, branched or PAMAM-NH₂ dendrimer [37–42].

The objective of this paper is to introduce a bottom-up synthesis of CQDs, using activated carbon as a precursor. These CQDs are functionalized with PAMAM-NH₂ and used for the detection of 4-chloro-2,6-dinitroaniline, a nitrocompound characteristic to explosives. The detection is based on ratiometric fluorescence method by using the ratio of fluorescence intensities at 465 and 507 nm I_{465}/I_{507} .

2. Experimental

2.1. Chemicals and materials

Activated carbon (100 mesh particle size, powder), polyamidoamine dendrimer-1,12-diaminododecane 4-chloro-2,6-dinitroaniline core generation 4 (PAMAM-NH₂G₄, solution in methanol 10%), 2,6-dichloro-4-nitroaniline (96%, 2,6DC-4NA), 2,5-dichloro-4-nitroaniline (97%, 2,5DC-4NA), 6-chloro-2,4-dinitroaniline (97%, 6C-2,4DNA) and (98%, 4C-2,6DNA) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich Spain; sulfuric acid (H₂SO₄, 99.999%), potassium permanganate (KMnO₄, >99.0%) and hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂, 30%, p/v) were purchased from Merck, Darmstadt (Germany). Deionized water with resistivity higher than 4MΩ/cm was used.

2.2. Synthesis, purification

Ground activated carbon (200 mg) and KMnO₄ (1.2 g) were added to concentrated sulfuric acid (95%, 12 mL) and then the suspension obtained was stirred for 1 h. After this, deionized H₂O (25 mL) was added and the mixture was heated 90 °C for 30 min. This solution was left at room temperature until it reached 60 °C. Then H₂O₂ (2 mL) was added with continuous stirring for 30 min. After centrifugation, ethyl acetate (40 mL) was added to the water suspension of CQDs to purify them. Then the organic phase was evaporated under N₂ and CQDs were re-dissolved in water (20 mL). The pH of this solution was adjusted to 7 with NaOH 1 M. As a next step the dialysis of the solution was carried out versus water. To obtain CQDs@PAMAM-NH₂, same procedure was carried out. Briefly, to CQDs (500 μL) obtained previously, PAMAM-NH₂ dendrimer (10 μL) was added and the solution was stirred for 48 h. To control the functionalization, fluorescence measurements at 465 nm were recorded with excitation at 365 nm.

2.3. Methods

Absorbance was measured on a Hewlett-Packard HP8452A diode array spectrophotometer. Infrared measurements were carried out using a Bruker Equinox 55 FT-IR spectrometer fitted with a Golden Gate single reflection ATR accessory kit from Specac. All spectra were collected using a resolution of 2 cm⁻¹ and 50 scans

were collected. Raman measurements were carried out on a Sen Terra dispersive Raman spectrometer (Bruker with 785 nm as excitation). The back Raman scattering was collected with a standard spectral resolution of 3 cm⁻¹, spatial resolution of 0.5 μm, and spot size of about 3 μm. X-ray photoelectron spectroscopic (XPS) studies were performed on a Physical Electronic PHI 5700 spectrometer using non-monochromatic Mg-K_α radiation (300 W, 15 kV and 1253.6 eV) for analyzing the core-level signals of the elements of interest with a hemispherical multichannel detector. The spectra of powdered samples were recorded with a constant pass energy value at 29.35 eV, using a 720 μm diameter circular analysis area. The X-ray photoelectron spectra obtained were analyzed using PHI ACESS ESCA-V6.0F software and processed using MultiPak 8.2B package. The binding energy values were referenced to adventitious carbon C 1s signal (284.8 eV). Shirley-type background and Gauss-Lorentz curves were used to determine the binding energies. Zeta potential measurements (ζ). ζ of CQDs was determined using a Zetasizer Nano ZS (Malvern Instruments, U.K.) equipped with a 4 mW HeNe laser operating at λ = 633 nm ζ measurements were performed at 25 °C in polycarbonate folded capillary cells, with Au plated electrodes (DTS1061). Deionized H₂O was the dispersion medium. The different ζ were automatically obtained by the software, using the Stokes-Einstein and the Henry equation, with the Smoluchowski approximation. Photoluminescence spectrophotometer (Horiba Jovin Yvon Fluoromax 4 TCSPC) was used to characterize CQDs optical performance. The fluorescence was measured in the wavelength range of 300–650 nm. The spectra were obtained with an integration time of 0.1 s and 1 nm slits for excitation and emission. All measurements were performed at room temperature. Fluorescence lifetime analysis was done using an Edinburgh Instruments FLS920, equipped with a Xe lamp (450 W) as excitation source for steady state fluorescence measurements and mono-chromatics LEDs (PicoQuant PLS), controlled by a PDL 880-B system. Fluorescence decays were interpreted in terms of a multi-exponential: $I(t) = A + \sum B_i e^{-t/\tau_i}$, where A and B_i are the pre-exponential factors and τ_i the decay times.

2.4. Fluorescence ratiometric determination of 4-chloro-2,6-dinitroaniline

Previous the study of the quenching effect of 4C-2,6DNA, the effects of this and other nitrocompounds were studied by addition of nitrocompounds stock solutions (8×10^{-5} M) to 10 μL of CQDs@PAMAM-NH₂ to the desired concentrations levels in 1 mL quartz cuvette. The mixture was then equilibrated at room temperature for 5 min before the spectral measurements at 465 and 507 nm. To assess the selectivity of this sensor was carried out with related nitrocompounds, such as 2,6DC-4NA, 2,5DC-4NA and 6C-2,4DNA at different 4C-2,6DNA/nitrocompound ratio concentrations (3:1; 1:1; 1:3). Data were obtained by the following relationship:

$$\text{Ratio} = \frac{(465/507)_{\text{CQDs@PAMAM-NH}_2: 4\text{C-2,6DNA-Nitrocompound}}}{(465/507)_{\text{CQDs@PAMAM-NH}_2: 4\text{C-2,6DNA}}}$$

where the quotient between the ratios of the fluorescence of the solutions of CQDs@PAMAM-NH₂ with 4C-2,6DNA interacts at I_{465}/I_{507} with the different selected nitrocompounds as interferences (dividend), and without the interference (divisor). In other words, the fluorescence at different peaks was recorded and the ratio obtained with this equation.

QY was determined using quinine sulfate Rhodamine as standard, which according literature has a QY of 0.54 in 0.1 M H₂SO₄ (n = 1.38). Both nanoparticles were dissolved in distilled water

($n = 1.33$). The integrated area under the fluorescence curves (excitation at 470 nm) was plotted versus the absorbance at 370 nm (after subtraction of the solvent absorbance) for different concentrations. The excitation intensity and slit width were held constant for all measurements. The QY of the CQDs was obtained from:

$$QY_{\text{CQDs}} = \left[\frac{I_{\text{CQDs}}}{I_{\text{ref}}} \right] \left(\frac{2_{\text{CQDs}}}{n_{\text{st}}^2} \right)$$

where I is the area under the fluorescence curves and A is the corresponding absorbance [43].

3. Results and discussion

The synthetic route used for the preparation of CQDs from activated carbon is an exhausted oxidation process, which consists of the isolation of the nanostructures and oxidation of their edges. The CQDs obtained are well dispersed and have a uniform size distribution in water. Despite of the general affinity of CQDs to a solvent of a low polarity, the re-dissolution in water at neutral pH was used having in mind CQDs application as a sensor. CQDs exhibit green fluorescence when are irradiated with UV light (365 nm, see Fig S1, in Supplementary Information), however the colour of a purified solution is light brown. The source material, activated carbon was selected due to its low cost, little toxicity and easiness to oxidize [14].

3.1. Characterization of CQDs and CQDs@PAMAM-NH₂

The size and morphology of CQDs and CQDs@PAMAM-NH₂ nanoparticles were characterized by TEM (Fig. 1). TEM images (Fig. 1A, Fig. S2A) show a spherical morphology and narrow size distribution from 7 to 22 nm for CQDs, with a mean value of 12 ± 3.12 nm. The average particle size of the CQDs@PAMAM-NH₂

Fig. 2. UV-visible spectra of purified CQDs and functionalized with PAMAM dendrimer (CQDs@PAMAM-NH₂). (A colour version of this figure can be viewed online.)

ranges from 25 to 110 nm due to the formation of spherical aggregates, which, according to the size distribution histogram, have a mean diameter of 65 ± 5.33 nm (Fig. 1B, Fig. S2B).

The optical spectra of purified CQDs and CQDs@PAMAM-NH₂ displayed in Fig. 2 reveal two distinct peaks at 230/229 and 262/272 nm, respectively. They arise due to $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$, $n \rightarrow \sigma^*$ and $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions associated with C=C and carbonyl/hydroxyl groups, respectively [44]. In CQDs, there are no classical bandgap absorptions, so the surface defect states must be accessed directly from the ground state. Therefore, the trapping of excited state energy

Fig. 1. TEM images of purified (A) CQDs and (B) functionalized with PAMAM dendrimer CQDs@PAMAM-NH₂. (A colour version of this figure can be viewed online.)

probably occurs between the defects responsible for absorptions and those for emission. One may thus expect a broad distribution of excitations, corresponding to mostly featureless absorption spectra, as those typically observed for CQDs [45].

ATR-FTIR spectra of CQDs and coated with PAMAM-NH₂ counterpart (Fig. S3) reveal bands at 1677 and 1743 cm⁻¹, respectively. They represent carbonyls (C=O) and their presence is supported by the bands ascribed to C–OH at 1211 cm⁻¹ (CQDs), and the band at 1373 cm⁻¹ observed only for CQDs@PAMAM-NH₂. The band centered at 1077 cm⁻¹ is ascribed to the overlapping of C–H deformations and stretching vibrations of C–O (ether) and C–C. A very broad and intense band at 3327 cm⁻¹ and the band centered at 1071 cm⁻¹ represent the stretching vibrations and in-plane bending vibration of –OH, respectively. The N–H stretching vibrations occur near 3300–3500 cm⁻¹ and they overlap with the –OH stretching band. The emerging band at 1633 cm⁻¹ on the spectra for CQDs@PAMAM-NH₂ indicates the presence of amide from PAMAM-NH₂ dendrimer. The 785 nm laser wavelength Raman spectra of CQDs (Fig. S4), show a strong feature at 989 cm⁻¹, related to the vibration of sp² bonded carbon atoms in a two dimensional hexagonal lattice of graphite structure. It is interesting that on the Raman spectra G (1600 cm⁻¹) and D (1300–1350 cm⁻¹) bands typical for carbon materials do not appear.

The negative ζ of CQDs nanoparticles (-18.50 mV) is due to the presence of deprotonated carboxyl groups on the nanoparticles surface. The negative ζ value is linked to the oxidation effect of the sulfuric acid, which results in carboxylic acids as main functional groups.

The surface composition of CQDs obtained from activated carbon was evaluated using XPS (Fig. S5.) These results indicate that our CQDs are composed, of C, O, N, Na, Si, Cl and S, and their atomic concentrations % is shown in Table 1. The presence of Na, Si, Cl is likely related to the ash content in the parent carbon and the synthesis procedure.

The C 1s core level spectrum (Fig. 3A) can be decomposed into three contributions, corresponding to C–C at a binding energy of 284.8 eV (77%), O–C=O at 287.3 eV (5%) and $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ at 291.0 eV (18%). The O 1s signal is decomposed into two contributions (Fig. 3B) with binding energy at 530.2 (C=O) and 531.7 (C–O) eV [46]. After the incorporation of the dendrimer, the same elements are found on the surface but the surface chemical composition changes (see Table 1). As expected, a clear increase of in the C and N content is visible due to the incorporation of the dendrimer molecules containing nitrogen in its functional groups. The C 1s core energy level spectrum of sample CQDs@PAMAM-NH₂ (Fig. 3C) is also deconvoluted into three components, corresponding to C–C at a binding energy of 284.8 eV, (72%), O–C=O at 287.0 eV (16%) and $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ at 290.7 eV (12%). The contribution at 287.0 eV increases due to the presence of amide groups. The N 1s core energy level spectrum is asymmetric (Fig. 3D) and is deconvoluted into two contributions at 398.4 eV (81%) and 399.9. eV (19%) assigned to amide and amine groups, respectively [47].

Fig. 4A shows the room temperature fluorescence spectra of the CQDs and CQDs@PAMAM-NH₂, excited at 350 nm. As seen, the modification of CQDs with PAMAM-NH₂ dendrimer resulted in a significant increase (2 fold) in the fluorescence intensity. This indicates a protective effect of the dendrimer on the surface of the

Table 1
Surface chemical composition of CQDs and CQDs@PAMAM-NH₂ (in at. %).

	C	O	N	Na	S
CQDs	47.35	29.86	2.25	7.66	6.47
CQDs@PAMAM-NH ₂	55.48	25.53	6.50	6.10	4.83

Fig. 3. A) and B) C 1s, and O 1s core level spectra of CQDs synthesized from activated carbon. C) and D) C 1s and N 1s core level spectra of CQDs@PAMAM-NH₂. (A colour version of this figure can be viewed online.)

CQDs nanoparticles on the surroundings. It decreases the radiative effect from the excited state by increasing the fluorescence intensity. The fluorescence quantum yields (QY) of CQDs and CQDs@PAMAM-NH₂ were determined to be 3.94 and 6.93%, respectively. The N atoms in PAMAM dendrimer, and especially N-doping precursors and as surface passivating agents for CQDs. Their presence results in the enhanced fluorescence intensity and increases QY with an increase in N content [48].

Fig. 4. A) Fluorescence spectra of CQDs and CQDs@PAMAM-NH₂ with excitation at 350 nm). B) Fluorescence spectra of CQDs@PAMAM-NH₂ when excited at different wavelength. (A colour version of this figure can be viewed online.)

To further explore the optical properties of CQDs@PAMAM-NH₂, a detailed fluorescence study was carried out under various excitation wavelengths. As shown in Fig. 4B, when the excitation wavelength increases from 300 to 400 nm, the emission peak gradually blue-shifts to shorter wavelengths. Its intensity increases, which indicates an existence of different surface energy traps of CQDs@PAMAM-NH₂ than those in CQDs. They emit at 465 nm when excited at 350 nm. Consequently, the fluorescence dependence on the excitation wavelength cannot be ascribed to CQDs@PAMAM-NH₂ of different sizes. Therefore, the presence of various functional groups (C=O, C-OH, and C-N) on the CQDs@PAMAM-NH₂ could be responsible for at least 2 different emissive sites with different energy levels, as justified by the study of the fluorescence decay. This overall complexity behavior of the emission spectra is apparently associated with the variety of emission centers present in CQDs@PAMAM-NH₂.

The fluorescent lifetimes for CQDs and CQDs@PAMAM-NH₂ were calculated. The fluorescent decay curve was fitted to two exponential decay models. Table 2 shows the fluorescence lifetime parameters (A, B₁ and τ₁) and the fit (χ²) values. A short fluorescence lifetime (1.17 ns/1.01 ns) is similar to that of QDs, and reveals the radiative recombination nature of excitations [49]. The average fluorescence lifetimes of CQDs and CQDs@PAMAM-NH₂ are in the nanosecond range and they indicate that both CQDs and CQDs@PAMAM-NH₂ are suitable for sensor applications, because they are not susceptible to changes in an excitation light intensity, to photo-bleaching, and to variations in light scattering and absorption by the sample [50]. The fluorescence spectra (peak at 465 nm and intensity) were considered as unchanged for 6 months, when stored at 4° C, within the experimental errors. The effect of pH (2.5–11) on the fluorescence intensity of CQDs@PAMAM-NH₂ was studied (Fig. 5). With an increasing pH starting from 2.25, the fluorescence intensity increases drastically (~60%) and become constant from pH 6. We linked this trend to the buffering effect of the surface groups (-COOH and -NH₂ mainly). This is another important feature indicating the suitability of these materials for sensing applications.

3.2. CQDs@PAMAM-NH₂ as *fl*

To evaluate the feasibility of quenching-based nitro compound detection, and thus the application of our CQDs for sensing of explosives, the interactions of CQDs@PAMAM-NH₂ with target compounds were first evaluated. Fig. 6A shows the effect of the nitroaromatic compounds, 4C-2,6DNA, 6C-2,4DNA, 2,5DC-4NA and 2,6DC-4NA on the fluorescence spectra of CQDs@PAMAM-NH₂ nanoparticles. The results show that these species quench the fluorescence in a marked way. It is interesting that the addition of 4C-2,6DNA quenched the fluorescence of CQDs@PAMAM-NH₂ differently that did the other three compounds and on the spectra a unique emission band at 507 nm emerges at the expense of the decrease intensity of the band at 465 nm. On other hand, the two shoulders of the emission bands at 465 and 507 nm decreased at different ratios because of the presence of 4C-2,6DNA that quenches the emission. Fig. 6B presents the correlation between the intensity ratios of the emission at 465 nm to that at 507 nm (I₄₆₅/I₅₀₇). Based on the results collected, 4C-2,6DNA was selected as a detection target owing to its presence in explosives as a powerful initiator [51] and due to its highest toxicity among all four species tested.

The quenching of CQDs@PAMAM-NH₂ fluorescence by 4C-2,6DNA was rapid and sensitive to the presence of the target molecule, even at a very low concentration. After 1 h exposure the fluorescence intensity remained stable. A charge transfer process could be a possible mechanism for the CQDs@PAMAM-NH₂ fluorescence quenching by 4C-2,6DNA. Since the maximum absorption band of 4C-2,6DNA centers at 440 nm in aqueous media [52], it overlaps with the emission band of CQDs@PAMAM-NH₂, giving rise to an energy transfer process. These results in the formation of a

Table 2
Fluorescence lifetime for CQDs and CQDs@PAMAM-NH₂.

	CQDs	CQDs@PAMAM-NH ₂
A	3.021	1.496
B ₁	0.063	0.064
B ₂	0.0087	0.0074
τ ₁ (ns)	1.174 (60.95%)	1.011 (64.93%)
τ ₂ (ns)	5.403 (39.1%)	4.758 (35.07%)
χ ²	1.294	1.093

Fig. 5. Influence of the pH on the fluorescence intensity of CQDs@PAMAM-NH₂ with excitation at 350 nm. (A colour version of this figure can be viewed online.)

complex in which the negative charge is delocalized over the cyclohexadienine ring and the nitro group and the positive charge is distributed over an iminium group, known as Meisenheimer complex (Fig. 7) [53]. The formation of such complex with amino groups is typical for of nitroaromatic compounds. In our case, the amine groups of PAMAM-NH₂ dendrimer contribute to this complexation [54]. The two electron-withdrawing nitro groups in 4C-2,6DNA enable the aniline ring to be electron-poor donating, but enough to form a stable complex, which is observed at 507 nm.

Under the optimum conditions determined in our experimental procedure, the Stern-Volmer formalism indicates that there is a linear relationship between the change in the fluorescence intensity at 465 nm and the concentration of 4C-2,6DNA over the range 1.0×10^{-5} – 6.0×10^{-4} M, ($I_f = 1 + 23108 [4C-2,6DNA]$ with $r = 0.994$) with a $K_{SV} = 23108 \text{ M}^{-1}$ (inset Fig. 6B). The results collected in Table 3 suggest that a static mechanism is predominant in the quenching of the fluorescence intensity of CQDs@PAMAM-NH₂ by 4C-2,6DNA. In the case of pure static quenching the lifetime is unaffected by the presence of quencher and a plot of τ_0/τ versus $[Q]$ is expected to give a linear relationship. Results collected in Table 3 follow this pattern [55].

Calculated detection (LOD) and sensitivity limits of 4C-2,6DNA are 2.57 and 111.6 μM , respectively. The repeatability, expressed as standard relative deviation (RSD, $n = 10$) was 0.85% at the concentration level of 10 μM of 4C-2,6DNA. When unmodified CQDs, without functionalization with PAMAM-NH₂ dendrimer, were used a LOD and sensitivity limits of 5.19 μM and 27.0 μM , respectively, were obtained with RSD = 1.65%. Thus the presence of the dendrimer in the system improves the analytical signal. These differences demonstrate the feasibility of the proposed functionalization of CQDs for the detection of explosives.

Systems based in fluorescence spectroscopy to detect TNT or DNT at 30 and 40.7 μM , using molecularly imprinting polymer, have been addressed in the literature [56]. For this purpose functionalized ZnS-Mn nanoparticles [57] or CdSe coated with PAMAM-NH₂ [58] were used. The detection sensitivity was 1 nM or 0.01 ppm, respectively. A hybrid capped mesoporous material, which was selectively opened in the presence of Tetryl and TNT, has been synthesized and used for the fluorogenic recognition at ppm range [59]. TNT has been also quantified electrochemically using CQDs as electrode on the level of nM. Nevertheless, when CQDs was used as

Fig. 6. A) Effect of nitroaromatic compounds (8×10^{-5} M) on the fluorescence spectrum of the CQDs@PAMAM-NH₂. B) Influence of the [4C-2,6DNA] on the fluorescence spectra of CQDs@PAMAM-NH₂ (10 mL in 1 final volume: a) 0 M, b) 1×10^{-5} M, c) 2×10^{-5} M, d) 4×10^{-5} M, e) 8×10^{-5} M, f) 1.2×10^{-4} M, g) 1.6×10^{-4} M, h) 2.4×10^{-4} M, i) 3.2×10^{-4} and j) 6×10^{-4} M (Inset Stern-Volmer model). (A colour version of this figure can be viewed online.)

a fluorescence sensor the detection level was in μM range [60].

To assess the possibility of the analytical application of our nanosensor CQDs in terms of its sensitivity, the effect of different concentration ratios of several nitrocompounds (2,6DC-4NA, 2,5DC-4NA and 6C-2,4DNA) to that of 4C-2,6DNA (8.0×10^{-5} M), on the fluorescence intensity of CQDs@PAMAM-NH₂ was studied. The fluorescence intensities of CQDs@PAMAM-NH₂, at different concentration ratios (3:1; 1:1 and 1:3) were measured in separate sets of experiments and the results are summarized in Table 4 and (Fig S6). Recoveries are the quantities observed value obtained using an analytical procedure that involves a calibration graph [61]. 4C-2,6DNA shows recoveries between 100 and 117% and an accuracy as between 1.0 and 2.8% as RSD. The proposed method demonstrates its feasibility of the CQDs@PAMAM-NH₂ nanoparticle application as 4C-2,6DNA sensor.

The results presented in this study indicate that the fluorescent-CQDs@PAMAM-NH₂ CQDs are a feasible medium for detecting explosives. They show the high sensitivity and selectivity for the specific nitrocompounds detection. Sensing is based on a marked quenching in the fluorescence signal.

Fig. 7. Possible charge transfer mechanism of CQDs@PAMAM-NH₂ in presence of 4C-2,6DNA. (A colour version of this figure can be viewed online.)

Table 3

Lifetime intensity decays of CQDs@PAMAM-NH₂ nanoparticles in H₂O in the presence of 4C-2,6DNA.

4C-2,6DNA (M)	τ (ns)
0	3.09
1.0×10^{-5}	3.31
2.0×10^{-5}	3.30
4.0×10^{-5}	3.60
8.0×10^{-5}	3.25
1.2×10^{-4}	4.08

Table 4

Interferences of other related nitrocompounds on the determination of the 4C-2,6DNA (8.0×10^{-5} M), expressed in recoveries (%) for $n = 3$.^a

Recovery (%)			
	3:1	1:1	1:3
6C-2,4DNA	101.9 (1.03)	105.9 (1.35)	117.8 (2.46)
2,5DC-4NA	100.5 (1.22)	116.5 (1.96)	104.0 (2.67)
2,6DC-4NA	104.1 (1.66)	104.0 (2.67)	102.8 (2.03)

^a In parenthesis the standard deviation.

4. Conclusions

In summary, a novel approach for the fluorimetric sensing of nitroaromatic explosives using carbon quantum dots coated with PAMAM-NH₂ dendrimer nanoparticles has been reported. The presence of the explosive 4C-2,6DNA in an aqueous solution was detected at a low concentration based on the change of a fluorescence signal as a result of CQDs-target molecule interactions. In particular, the functionalization of the external surface with the PAMAM-NH₂ dendrimer, and its interactions with electron-deficient groups of the explosive 4C-2,6DNA (to enhance or tune selectivity), which lead to the strong signal, make this approach appealing for the potential sensing applications.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data related to this article can be found at <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.carbon.2016.05.030>.

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